

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

CEBPG supports luminal B lineage commitment.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We conducted an expression screen to discover genes important for lineage specification during bifurcation of the PAM50 molecular subtypes luminal A and luminal B. We identified activation of CEBPG in luminal B subtype breast cancers. CEBPG likely supports luminal B lineage commitment.